

Development of a de-welding on demand concept for resistance welding of GFR-PA6.6 for controlled disassembly and repair

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Project TTP-LB Dom4Composites

- **Project Objectives:** Recycling-optimized lightweight construction through modular design for dismountable structural components
- Investigation of dismountable component joints using electric resistance welding and Intermoulding
- Debonding / de-welding on demand of thermoplastic material in the joining area
- Life cycle and sustainability analysis for all concepts developed in the project

Partners:

CarbonTT, NK, fibretech composites, Fraunhofer IFAM, Fraunhofer IGP, Henkel, HWH HARMS+WENDE

Electrical resistance welding (ERW)

Heating elements for electrical resistance welding

GF fabric 0°; 90°
(80 g/m²) (Isolation)

GF fabric +45°; -45°
(80 g/m²) (Isolation)

PA6-film (t = 100 μm) /
PA6.6-film (t = 65 μm) /
PP-g-MAH film (t = 100 μm)

Stainless steel mesh
(wire diameter: d = 65 μm)

Manufactured in the hot press

“Softened Hybrid”

- Utilize temperature dependent softening of polymers at high temperatures
- To avoid delamination, the heat affected zone should be small or the material at the interface needs to melt “early”
- Hybrid material needed to focus breaking into interface

→ Hybrid-material welding enables debonding via reheating of heating element

“Induction”

- Similarly to the Softened-hybrid concept, material at interface is softened at high temperatures
- Utilizes high frequency induction, heating the resistance welding element
- Heat so fast, that heat can’t spread via conduction

→ Heating \gg Thermal Conduct. avoiding delamination during inductive debonding

“Brittle Hybrid”

- Cool polymers to become more brittle, making them easier to break
- Utilize strain-hardening of viscoelastic materials:
 - Lower temperatures, or
 - higher loading rates
- Hybrid material needed to focus breaking into interface

→ From quasi-static towards dynamic/impact debonding at low temperatures

“Softened Hybrid concept”

De-welding-on-demand concept “Softened Hybrid”: PA6 and PA6.6 during service life

Maximum single lap shear strength at room temperature

Single lap shear configuration

- Preliminary shear strength (no DoE yet)
- Highest shear strengths with pure PA6
- Reduction in shear strength for hybrid heating element at approx. 14 %
 - Welding of de-welding-on-demand concept successful

De-welding-on-demand concept "Softened Hybrid": Temperature-dependent stiffness of PA6.6 & PA6

De-welding-on-demand concept “Softened Hybrid”: Single lap shear strength at debonding

Maximum single lap shear strength
at room temperature and 220 °C

- Hybrid weld achieves SLS-strength of approx.
 - 17 MPa (RT)
 - 1 MPa (220 °C)
- ... while pure PA6.6 achieves approx.
 - 6 MPa (220 °C)

- Without using the hybrid heating element, residual single lap shear strength still high after application of stimulus at 220 °C
- PA6.6 not heated above its T_m (PA6.6) = 260 °C

- Effective reduction of the single lap shear strength through an external stimulus without damaging the adherends

De-welding-on-demand concept "Softened Hybrid": Qualitative analysis of de-welding in SLS configuration

Single lap shear strength of hybrid weld at 23 °C

- At RT, the test specimens show a **brittle fracture** as plastics do in a glassy state
- No plastic flow detectable

- At $T = 220 \text{ °C}$, the test specimens show **viscoelastic / viscoplastic behavior**
- The adherends show no damage/delamination, as they are made of PA6.6 as $T_m(\text{PA6}) < T_m(\text{PA6.6})$

Single lap shear strength of hybrid weld at 220 °C

De-welding-on-demand concept “Softened Hybrid”: Micro-CT and fracture surfaces

- No damage to the surface and no delamination detectable for de-welding at 220 °C
- At RT specimens show near surface failure
- After heating, the specimens show failure of the polymer matrix at the stainless steel heating element

De-welding-on-demand concept „Softened Hybrid“
successful!

“Induction concept”

De-welding-on-demand concept "induction": Initial heating trials of resistance welding element

Induction tests with resist. heating element (HE)

Thermographic video of the induction test of an HE

Distance: 10 mm | Duration: 0.5 sec. |
Frequency: 1095 kHz

Comparison HE after induction test

“Brittle-hybrid concept”

De-welding-on-demand concept “Brittle-Hybrid”: PP-g-MAH leads to drastic reduction in service life

Maximum single lap shear strength at room temperature:
Hybrid Concept based of PA66/PA6 vs Concept based on
PA6/PP-g-MAH

- Brittle fracture of PP as de-welding-on-demand concept
- Heating element made from Polypropylene-graft-maleic anhydride (PP-g-MAH) for polarizing of PP in order to make it compatible with highly polar PA6

Will not be pursued further, as the mechanical properties at RT (utilization phase) are reduced too much

- If resistance or induction welding is used to join thermoplastic composites:
 - heating element / susceptor material may be used for debonding purpose
- Using “weld-compatible” polymers with different T_m or T_g (if amorphous), separating (**de-welding**) of adherends is possible without damaging them **by matrix-hybrid heating elements / susceptors!**
 - Influence on SLS strength at room temperature is comparatively small
 - Absolute SLS strength in combination with qualitative analysis of polymer rheology helps finding optimal de-welding temperature!

Next steps:

- New experiments at $T_m(\text{PA6}) = 220\text{ °C} \ll T_{\text{de-welding}} < T_m(\text{PA6.6}) = 260\text{ °C}$ to further lower single lap shear strength at de-welding
- Use of carbon-fiber based heating elements instead of stainless steel
- Adaptability to amorphous Elium® resins for composites by Arkema, which is a material enabling thermoplastic pultrusion
- Application in a demonstrator of a large structure on a bulk carrier (Hatch cover)

OpenAI: DALL·E

Thank you for your attention!

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